

Long-Term Safety and Efficacy of the Fixed-Dose Combination of Pertuzumab and Trastuzumab for Subcutaneous Injection in Patients With HER2-Positive Early Breast Cancer in PHranceSCa, a Randomized, Open-Label Phase II Study

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Abstract

After 3 years' follow-up in PHranceSCa (NCT03674112), there were no grade 4/5 adverse events in the continuation period; the invasive disease-free survival event-free rate was 94.17% (95% confidence interval, 90.47-97.87); and the overall survival event-free rate was 98.71% (96.92-100). PHranceSCa adds to the totality of evidence reinforcing the long-term clinical benefit and safety of pertuzumab and trastuzumab.

Background: We assessed long-term safety, efficacy, and health-related quality of life during the continuation phase after 3 years' follow-up in PHranceSCa (NCT03674112). **Patients and Methods:** This was a randomized, open-label, international, multicenter, crossover, Phase II study in adjuvant HER2-positive early breast cancer. One hundred fifty nine patients received 3 cycles of the fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC), then 3 of intravenous pertuzumab and trastuzumab (P + H IV), or *vice versa*. Postcrossover, patients continued preferred treatment (≤ 18 cycles total). **Results:** Most adverse events, including all cardiac events ($n = 2$) and anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity ($n = 3$) were grade 1/2. None were grade 4/5. Grade 1/2 local injection-site reactions

Abbreviations: AE, adverse event; CI, confidence interval; DDFS, distant disease-free survival; EORTC QLQ-C30, European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life of Cancer Patients Core Questionnaire; FDC, fixed-dose combination; H, trastuzumab; HRQoL, health-related quality of life; IDFS, invasive disease-free survival; IV, intravenous; MedDRA, Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities; OS, overall survival; P, pertuzumab; SC, subcutaneous.

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occurred in 13 patients (9.4%) receiving PH FDC SC. Other events occurred at comparable rates between arms. The overall event-free rate for invasive disease-free survival was 94.17% (95% confidence interval, 90.47-97.87) at 3 years; overall survival was 98.71% (96.92-100). Meaningful changes from baseline in health-related quality of life included improvements in role and social functioning, and reductions in financial difficulty. **Conclusion:** PH FDC SC was well tolerated, with safety consistent with that of P + H IV (except local injection-site reactions) and no grade ≥ 3 anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity or new safety signals in the continuation period. Immature efficacy data showed high event-free rates, consistent with the known clinical benefit of pertuzumab and trastuzumab (although follow-up was relatively short at 3 years). PHranceSCa adds to the totality of evidence reinforcing the long-term clinical benefit and safety of pertuzumab and trastuzumab.

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Keywords: Adjuvant therapy, Adverse events, Invasive disease-free survival, Overall survival, Health-related quality of life

Introduction

Intravenous pertuzumab plus trastuzumab (P + H IV) in combination with chemotherapy has long been the standard of care for HER2-positive early and metastatic breast cancer;¹⁻³ however, total administration time can amount to several hours due to sequential infusions and observation, cannulation, line flushing, and waiting times. This places a burden on patients and healthcare systems.⁴⁻⁶

A fixed-dose combination of P + H for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC; pertuzumab/trastuzumab/hyaluronidase-zzxf) was therefore developed, with the aim of offering less invasive and faster administration than IV infusion. PH FDC SC is injected in ~ 8 minutes (loading doses) and ~ 5 minutes (maintenance) and has shorter observation times than P + H IV (minimum 30 and 15 minutes, respectively).

PH FDC SC plus chemotherapy for HER2-positive early breast cancer was investigated in the randomized, open-label, multicenter, noninferiority, Phase III FeDeriCa study. PH FDC SC was noninferior to P + H IV in terms of cycle 7 P serum trough concentrations, with comparable total pathologic complete response rates and safety profiles in the neoadjuvant phase of the study.⁷ In the adjuvant phase, safety remained comparable (except for adverse events [AEs] associated with SC vs IV administration).⁸ AE incidence rates were also balanced across patient body weight quartiles within treatment arms, between treatment arms, and within the lowest body weight quartile.⁸

The randomized, open-label, multicenter, crossover Phase II PHranceSCa study focused on determining patient preference for route of P + H administration in the adjuvant setting.⁹ After experiencing 3 cycles of each, 85% of patients preferred PH FDC SC over P + H IV (most had a strong preference).⁹ PH FDC SC was generally well tolerated, with no new safety signals (even when switching between routes).⁹

In this follow-up analysis, we report long-term safety, efficacy, and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) data after treatment continuation and follow-up.

Patients and Methods

Study Design and Patients

Details have been published.⁹ Briefly, eligible patients ($N = 160$) were randomized 1:1 to 3 PH FDC SC cycles (P 600 mg/H 600 mg

in 10 mL) followed by 3 P + H IV cycles (P 420 mg; H 6 mg/kg) or 3 P + H IV cycles followed by 3 PH FDC SC cycles. If needed, loading doses were P 1200 mg/H 600 mg in 15 mL for PH FDC SC and P 840 mg/H 8 mg/kg for P + H IV. After the crossover period, patients continued treatment via their preferred method (continuation period, ≤ 18 cycles total).

PHranceSCa was conducted in accordance with Good Clinical Practice guidelines and the Declaration of Helsinki. The protocol was reviewed and approved by the institutional review board/ethics committee at each study site. All patients provided written informed consent.

Outcomes

Endpoints presented are safety, invasive disease-free survival (IDFS), IDFS including second primary non-breast cancer, distant disease-free survival (DDFS), overall survival (OS), and HRQoL after 3 years' follow-up.

Statistical Analysis

Safety was assessed in all patients who received ≥ 1 dose of any study drug; efficacy, in all randomized patients (intention-to-treat population); HRQoL, in patients in the intention-to-treat population with a baseline European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life of Cancer Patients Core Questionnaire (EORTC QLQ-C30) assessment and ≥ 1 postbaseline EORTC QLQ-C30 assessment.

AEs were graded using National Cancer Institute Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events v4.0. IDFS, IDFS including second primary non-breast cancer, DDFS, and OS were assessed using the Kaplan–Meier method; HRQoL, as change from baseline in EORTC QLQ-C30 scores. Analyses were performed using SAS, version 9.4 (SAS Institute, Inc., Cary, NC).

Results

Patients

Of 160 patients treated, 159 entered the continuation period; 138 chose PH FDC SC; 21, P + H IV (Supplemental Figure 1); 148 completed follow-up. Clinical cutoff was November 17, 2022. Median duration of follow-up was similar between arms: 36.3 months (range, 6-44 months) in the P + H IV–PH FDC SC arm and 37.1 months (7-45) in the PH FDC SC–P + H IV arm.

Table 1 Summary of Safety During the Continuation Period

Patients, n (%)	PH FDC SC Continuation (n = 138)	P + H IV Continuation (n = 21)
Any AE	92 (66.7)	14 (66.7)
Grade 3 AE*	7 (5.1)	2 (9.5)
Serious AE	4 (2.9)	0
Cardiac AE	1 (0.7)	1 (4.8)
Grade ≥ 3	0	0
Anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity	2 (1.4)	0
Grade ≥ 3	0	0
Administration-related reaction	16 (11.6)	1 (4.8)
Local injection-site reaction	13 (9.4)	0
Systemic injection reaction	2 (1.4)	0
Systemic infusion reaction	0	1 (4.8)
Grade ≥ 3 administration-related reaction	0	0
AE leading to dose interruption	8 (5.8)	1 (4.8)
AE leading to treatment discontinuation	0	1 (4.8)
AEs with incidence of ≥ 5% during the continuation period (any grade)		
Diarrhea	15 (10.9)	4 (19.0)
Injection-site reaction	13 (9.4)	0
Arthralgia	6 (4.3)	3 (14.3)
Fatigue	7 (5.1)	1 (4.8)
Pruritus	7 (5.1)	0
Pain in extremity	4 (2.9)	2 (9.5)
Rash	2 (1.4)	3 (14.3)
Headache	1 (0.7)	2 (9.5)
Myalgia	1 (0.7)	2 (9.5)
Bone pain	0	2 (9.5)

Coding was according to MedDRA v25.1.

Abbreviations: AE = adverse event; FDC = fixed-dose combination; H = trastuzumab; IV = intravenous; MedDRA = Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities; P = pertuzumab; SC = subcutaneous.

* No grade 4 or 5 adverse events were reported.

Patients received a median of 8 treatment cycles during continuation for P + H IV (range, 5-9) and PH FDC SC (3-10). A total of 97.5% (78/80) of patients in the P + H IV–PH FDC SC arm and 96.3% (77/80) in the PH FDC SC–P + H IV arm (96.9% [155/160] of all patients) had 18 neoadjuvant/adjuvant cycles in total.

Long-Term Safety

During the continuation period, most AEs, including all cardiac (n = 2) and anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity events (n = 3) were grade 1 and 2. No grade 4 or 5 AEs were reported. Grade 1-2 local injection-site reactions occurred in 13 patients (9.4%) receiving PH FDC SC. Other AEs occurred at comparable rates for PH FDC SC and P + H IV (Table 1).

Long-Term Efficacy

Overall, there were 11 (6.9%) IDFS events (Figure 1) and two deaths due to disease relapse and progressive disease. The overall 3-year IDFS rate was 94.17% (95% confidence interval [CI], 90.47-97.87). One additional event of second primary non-breast invasive cancer was observed (P + H IV–PH FDC arm). The overall 3-year OS rate was 98.71% (95% CI, 96.92-100). There were nine

(5.6%) DDFS events; the overall 3-year rate was 94.80% (95% CI, 91.30-98.31).

Long-Term HRQoL

Mean changes from baseline were minimal, with no meaningful differences between arms. The only changes from baseline considered clinically meaningful in either arm were improvements in role and social functioning and reduction in financial difficulties during follow-up (Figure 2).

Discussion

In this long-term follow-up analysis of the PHranceSCa study, PH FDC SC was well tolerated, with safety consistent with previous studies of P + H IV^{10,11} (except local injection-site reactions, which was as expected with SC administration) and no grade ≥ 3 anaphylaxis or hypersensitivity or new safety signals in the continuation period.

Immature efficacy data showed high event-free rates for IDFS and OS at 3 years, which were consistent with the known clinical benefit of P + H^{10,11} (although follow-up was relatively short at 3 years). IDFS including second primary non-breast cancer and DDFS data were consistent with IDFS findings. Patients’ role and

Figure 1 IDFS in the ITT population. Abbreviations: CNS = central nervous system; FDC = fixed-dose combination; H = trastuzumab; IDFS = invasive disease-free survival; ITT = intention-to-treat; IV = intravenous; mo = months; P = pertuzumab; SC = subcutaneous.

Figure 2 Changes in EORTC QLQ-C30 scores. Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Abbreviations: EORTC QLQ-C30 = European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life of Cancer Patients Core Questionnaire; FDC = fixed-dose combination; H = trastuzumab; HRQoL = health-related quality of life; IV = intravenous; P = pertuzumab; SC = subcutaneous.

social functioning scores showed clinically meaningful improvements, and there was meaningful reduction in financial difficulties during the follow-up period. This indicates an improvement in patients' abilities to engage in daily activities, an increase in their ability to pursue hobbies or leisure time activities, as well as reduced interference of their physical condition or medical treatment in family life, social activities, and finances.

The PHranceSCa study adds to the totality of evidence around the use of PH FDC SC as a flexible care option (i.e., treatment outside the clinic), which is especially important since flexible care has become increasingly vital to patients since the COVID-19 pandemic.¹² An expanded access study¹³ showed that safety of PH FDC SC at home was consistent with the established P + H safety profile and that it was preferred by patients over in-clinic P + H IV, indicating that at-home PH FDC SC is a viable option. In addition to the above-mentioned benefits of the SC formulation for patients, switching from P + H IV to PH FDC SC could also reduce loss of productivity,¹⁴ and could reduce non-drug costs for healthcare providers.¹⁵

Limitations of the analysis were that there was a small number of patients in the IV continuation group, and long-term efficacy data were immature. Considering that patients could receive their treatment of choice during the continuation period, any comparison between the randomized treatment arms following the crossover period should be interpreted with caution.

Conclusion

PHranceSCa adds to the totality of evidence reinforcing the long-term clinical benefit and safety of pertuzumab and trastuzumab.

Clinical Practice Points

- Intravenous pertuzumab plus trastuzumab (P + H IV) in combination with chemotherapy has long been the standard of care for HER2-positive early and metastatic breast cancer; however, total administration time can amount to several hours, which places a burden on patients and healthcare systems.
- Therefore, a fixed-dose combination of P + H for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC; pertuzumab/trastuzumab/hyaluronidase-zzxf) was developed, with the aim of offering less invasive and faster administration than IV infusion.
- After 3 years' follow-up, PH FDC SC was well tolerated. There was no grade ≥ 3 anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity or new safety signals during continuation.
- Efficacy was immature but showed high event-free invasive disease-free and overall survival rates (although follow-up was relatively short at 3 years).
- Role and social functioning improved meaningfully, and financial difficulties reduced meaningfully during follow-up (no differences between arms).
- PHranceSCa adds to the totality of evidence reinforcing the long-term clinical benefit and safety of P + H.

Previous Presentation

Presented in part at the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) Breast Cancer 2023 Annual Congress, Berlin, May 11-13, 2023. Poster 97P.

Data Sharing Statement

For eligible studies, qualified researchers may request access to individual patient-level clinical data through a data request platform. At the time of writing, this request platform is Vivli: <https://vivli.org/ourmember/roche/>. For up-to-date details on Roche's Global Policy on the Sharing of Clinical Information and how to request access to related clinical study documents, see here: https://go.roche.com/data_sharing. Anonymized records for individual patients across more than one data source external to Roche cannot, and should not, be linked due to a potential increase in risk of patient re-identification.

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Formal analysis. **Josefina Cruz:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Dame Lesley Fallowfield:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Päivi Auvinen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Catarina Pulido:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Ana Cvetanovic:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Sharon Wilks:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Leonor Ribeiro:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Mauricio Burotto:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Thomas Boulet:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Valentine Revelant:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Nathalie Theron:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Peter Trask:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Laurentia Wahyudi:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Zuzana Kirchmayer Machackova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ljiljana Stamatovic:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis.

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References

1. Burstein HJ, Curigliano G, Thürlimann B, et al. Customizing local and systemic therapies for women with early breast cancer: the St. Gallen International Consensus Guidelines for treatment of early breast cancer. *Ann Oncol.* 2021;32:1216–1235. doi:10.1016/j.annonc.2021.06.023.

2. Cardoso F, Kyriakides S, Ohno S, et al. Early breast cancer: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Ann Oncol.* 2019;30:1194–1220. doi:10.1093/annonc/mdz173.
3. AGO (German Gynecological Oncology Group). AGO breast cancer guidelines v1. 2020. Accessed 21 January, 2025. Available at: <https://www.ago-online.de>
4. Poorter RL, Lauw FN, Bemelman WA, Bakker PJM, Taat CW, Veenhof CHN. Complications of an implantable venous access device (Port-a-Cath) during intermittent continuous infusion of chemotherapy. *Eur J Cancer.* 1996;32A:2262–2266. doi:10.1016/s0959-8049(96)00274-2.
5. Shivakumar SP, Anderson DR, Couban S. Catheter-associated thrombosis in patients with malignancy. *J Clin Oncol.* 2009;27:4858–4864. doi:10.1200/JCO.2009.22.6126.
6. De Cock E, Pivrot X, Hauser N, et al. A time and motion study of subcutaneous versus intravenous trastuzumab in patients with HER2-positive early breast cancer. *Cancer Med.* 2016;5:389–397. doi:10.1002/cam4.573.
7. Tan AR, Im S-A, Mattar A, et al. Fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection plus chemotherapy in HER2-positive early breast cancer (FeDeriCa): a randomised, open-label, multicentre, non-inferiority, phase 3 study. *Lancet Oncol.* 2021;22:85–97. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30536-2.
8. Im SA, Tan AR, Mattar A, et al. Fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC) plus chemotherapy in HER2-positive early breast cancer (EBC): safety results from the adjuvant phase of the randomised, open-label, multicentre phase III (neo)adjuvant FeDeriCa study. *Ann Oncol.* 2021;32:S40–S41. doi:10.1016/j.annonc.2021.03.060.
9. O'Shaughnessy J, Sousa S, Cruz J, et al. Preference for the fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection in patients with HER2-positive early breast cancer (PHranceSCa): a randomised, open-label phase II study. *Eur J Cancer.* 2021;152:223–232. doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2021.03.047.
10. Gianni L, Pienkowski T, Im YH, et al. Efficacy and safety of neoadjuvant pertuzumab and trastuzumab in women with locally advanced, inflammatory, or early HER2-positive breast cancer (NeoSphere): a randomised multicentre, open-label, phase 2 trial. *Lancet Oncol.* 2012;13:25–32. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(11)70336-9.
11. von Minckwitz G, Procter M, de Azambuja E, et al. Adjuvant pertuzumab and trastuzumab in early HER2-positive breast cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2017;377:122–131. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1703643.
12. Wardley A, Canon JL, Elsten L, et al. Flexible care in breast cancer. *ESMO Open.* 2021;6:100007. doi:10.1016/j.esmoop.2020.100007.
13. Dang CT, Tolaney SM, Riaz F, et al. Preliminary analysis of an expanded access study of the fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab (P) and trastuzumab (H) for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC) for at-home administration (admin) in patients (pts) with HER2-positive (HER2+) breast cancer (BC) during the COVID-19 pandemic. *J Clin Oncol.* 2022;40:1515. doi:10.1200/JCO.2022.40.16_suppl.15.
14. Jackisch C, Manevy F, Frank S, Roberts N, Shafrin J. White paper on the value of time savings for patients and healthcare providers of breast cancer therapy: the fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection as an example. *Adv Ther.* 2022;39:833–844. doi:10.1007/s12325-021-01996-0.
15. Manevy F, Filkauskas G, Levy P, Fredriksson J, Sussell J. Potential non-drug cost differences associated with the use of the fixed-dose combination of pertuzumab and trastuzumab for subcutaneous injection (PH FDC SC) in the treatment of HER2-positive early breast cancer patients in Western Europe and the United States. *J Clin Oncol.* 2021;39:544. doi:10.1200/JCO.2021.39.15_suppl.5.

Supplementary materials

Supplemental Figure 1 CONSORT diagram. * One patient discontinued the crossover period after completing the crossover treatment, before starting the continuation period (after receiving cycle 6). † Patients who discontinued the period but remained in the study and continued into the follow-up period. Abbreviations: AE = adverse event; FDC = fixed-dose combination; H = trastuzumab; IV = intravenous; P = pertuzumab; SC = subcutaneous.

